

D5.6 — Report of “Implementation of existing workflows and toolkits for sensitive computing”

An ELIXIR Norway ELIXIR3 deliverable

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Context

This report describes work carried out for Deliverable 5.6, “Implementation of existing workflows and toolkits for sensitive computing”.

The deliverable builds on the D5.5 framework for making non-sensitive software components, such as BioContainers, available inside secure compute environments. The earlier D5.5 work identified CVMFS as a suitable mechanism for distributing read-only bioinformatics resources and software components into Trusted Research Environments such as TSD. The 2024 D5.5 report also described the evaluation of TSD security, compute, network, and storage requirements, and the ongoing establishment and testing of such infrastructure inside TSD.

The main achievement reported here is that this framework has now moved from planning and infrastructure assessment to practical availability: the Galaxy CVMFS (CernVM-File System) BioContainers repository was confirmed to be accessible inside the TSD/Colossus environment and usable as a software source for existing workflow/toolkit execution.

Background

Secure compute environments restrict direct internet access and uncontrolled software installation to protect sensitive research data. This is necessary, but it makes it difficult to run

modern bioinformatics workflows that depend on many tools, containers, and reference resources.

A central goal for D5.6 was therefore to demonstrate that existing tools and workflows can be made available inside such environments without manually importing and maintaining every software dependency inside each project.

CVMFS provides a practical solution by exposing centrally maintained, read-only software repositories inside the compute environment. For this deliverable, the key question was whether the Galaxy CVMFS BioContainers repository could be accessed and used from inside TSD/Colossus as part of the implementation of existing workflows and toolkits for sensitive computing.

Current challenges

Several challenges remain when implementing workflows and toolkits inside secure environments:

- secure environments usually do not provide direct internet access;
- workflow source code must be imported through approved channels;
- software dependencies must be made available in a controlled and reproducible way;
- containerized tools should be versioned and auditable;
- the user login environment and HPC execution environment may differ;
- workflow tools may expect Singularity while the platform provides Apptainer;
- reference files and input data must remain within the secure project area.

The work reported here focused on overcoming the most important infrastructure barrier: making the BioContainers software repository available inside the secure environment and confirming that it can be used from the TSD-associated HPC setting.

Delivery

Availability of Galaxy CVMFS BioContainers inside TSD/Colossus

A practical test was carried out in the TSD project [p3066](#), using the Colossus submit host:

p3066-hpc-01

The Galaxy CVMFS BioContainers repository was confirmed to be visible inside the environment at:

`/cvmfs/singularity.galaxyproject.org/all`

This is the central delivery point for D5.6: a major external software source for bioinformatics containers is available from inside the secure TSD/Colossus environment.

Verification of relevant BioContainers

Several BioContainers relevant to existing omics workflows were confirmed to be present in the mounted CVMFS repository, including:

```
fastqc:0.11.9--hdfd78af_1
multiqc:1.10.1--py_0
trimmomatic:0.39--1
bowtie2:2.4.5--py39hd2f7db1_2
samtools:1.6--hb116620_7
deeptools:3.5.0--py_0
picard:2.23.3--0
macs2:2.2.7.1--py39hbf8eff0_5
bedtools:2.30.0--hc088bd4_0
ucsc-bedgraphtobigwig:377--h446ed27_1
```

These tools cover common steps in genomics workflows, including raw-read quality control, trimming, mapping, alignment processing, signal generation, peak calling, and report aggregation.

Execution through Apptainer

The Colossus submit host provided Apptainer as the available container runtime:

```
apptainer version 1.5.0-1.el9
```

A direct execution test of a CVMFS-hosted BioContainer was successful:

```
apptainer exec /cvmfs/singularity.galaxyproject.org/all/fastqc:0.11.9--hdfd78af_1 fastqc
--version
```

This returned:

```
FastQC v0.11.9
```

This confirmed that the CVMFS repository was not only visible, but operationally usable as a source of executable BioContainers inside TSD/Colossus.

Use with existing workflow/toolkit structure

The availability of the CVMFS BioContainers repository was further tested with an existing ATAC-seq Snakemake workflow developed by Martina Visnovska¹. The workflow source was

¹ <https://gitlab.com/epigen/atacseqfastqtoreadcounts>

imported into TSD through the approved TSD portal mechanism and used as a representative existing workflow/toolkit for sensitive computing.

The test confirmed that an existing Snakemake workflow can be configured to resolve its containerized software dependencies from the CVMFS BioContainers repository inside TSD/Colossus.

The workflow was not treated as a production biological analysis in this deliverable. Instead, it was used to validate the implementation pattern: existing workflow source code inside TSD, software dependencies from CVMFS, and execution through the Colossus/Apptainer environment.

Initial workflow execution

Initial workflow execution was successfully demonstrated using lightweight test input.

The following workflow stages completed:

```
init
raw_data_qc
fastqc_raw
multiqc_raw
```

The successful FastQC and MultiQC execution demonstrates that existing workflow steps can use CVMFS-hosted BioContainers from inside the secure compute environment.

Generated outputs included FastQC reports and a MultiQC report:

```
sampleA_R1_fastqc.html
sampleA_R2_fastqc.html
sampleA_R1_fastqc.zip
sampleA_R2_fastqc.zip
multiqc_report.html
multiqc_data.json
multiqc.done
```

Outcomes

1. CVMFS BioContainers repository is available inside TSD/Colossus

The most important outcome is that the Galaxy CVMFS BioContainers repository is accessible from inside the TSD/Colossus environment used for the proof-of-concept.

This means that a large collection of externally maintained bioinformatics containers can be made available to secure workflows without manually importing each container into the project.

2. Containerized tools can be executed through Apptainer

The CVMFS-hosted BioContainers were executable through Apptainer on the Colossus submit host. This provides a practical runtime model for using existing BioContainers inside TSD.

3. Existing workflows can be connected to CVMFS software components

An existing Snakemake workflow was used to validate that workflow-level software dependencies can be resolved from the CVMFS repository. This demonstrates the practical implementation of existing workflows and toolkits for sensitive computing.

4. TSD and Colossus can support workflow execution using shared software resources

The work confirmed that TSD project storage, the Colossus submit host, Snakemake, Apptainer, and CVMFS can be combined into a working execution model for secure bioinformatics workflows.

5. Reduced need for manual software import

By using CVMFS-hosted BioContainers, projects can avoid repeatedly importing and maintaining separate copies of commonly used software containers. This improves reproducibility and reduces operational overhead.

Conclusion

D5.6 has demonstrated that existing workflows and toolkits can be implemented inside a secure computing setting using CVMFS-provided software components.

The key achievement is that the Galaxy CVMFS BioContainers repository is available inside TSD/Colossus and can be used as an executable software source through Apptainer. This was validated both by direct container execution and by running initial stages of an existing Snakemake workflow.

This result provides a practical bridge between the D5.5 framework and future workflow implementation work. It shows that secure analysis environments can use controlled, read-only, externally maintained software repositories while keeping sensitive data inside the Trusted Research Environment.

The next step is to extend this from lightweight proof-of-concept testing to realistic workflow runs, including full ATAC-seq processing and additional workflows such as RNA-seq and single-cell analysis.